

1 **Survival Phenotype, Selfish Individual versus Darwinian Phenotype**

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26

27 **Abstract**

28 Consider an infinitely large asexual population without mutations and direct
29 interactions. The activities of an individual determine the fecundity and the survival
30 probability of individuals, moreover each activity takes time. We view this population
31 model as a simple combination of life history and optimal foraging models. The
32 phenotypes are given by probability distributions on these activities. We concentrate on
33 the following phenotypes defined by optimization of different objective functions: selfish
34 individual (maximizes the average offspring number during life span), survival phenotype
35 (maximizes the probability of non-extinction of descendants) and Darwinian phenotype
36 (maximizes the phenotypic growth rate).

37 We find that the objective functions above can achieve their maximum at different
38 activity distributions, in general. We find that the objective functions above can achieve
39 their maximum at different activity distributions, in general. The novelty of our work is
40 that we let natural selection act on the different objective functions. Using the classical
41 Darwinian reasoning, we show that in our selection model the Darwinian phenotype
42 outperforms all other phenotypes.

43

44 **1. Introduction**

45 Here we consider an asexual, sufficiently large and non-ageing population (i.e.,
46 the survival rate and fecundity of individuals do not depend on their age) and the

47 generations are overlapping (i.e., parents and their offspring can reproduce at the same
48 time). We suppose that the individuals are engaged in different activities, which
49 determine the fecundity, and the survival rate. All activities have certain time durations.
50 We emphasize that there are no interactions between individuals. Our basic assumption is
51 that individuals may only differ in their activity distributions, but they are alike in all
52 other respects. Consequently, in the present model, the phenotypes are fully defined by
53 their activity distributions. Finally, we assume that mutation is absent.

54 We note that from the mathematical point of view, this selection situation is
55 possibly the first step towards a combination of life history theory (Stearns 1992,
56 Charnov 1993), and optimal foraging theory (Stephens & Krebs 1986), for it contains the
57 essential elements of both these theories. Namely, we work with overlapping generations
58 like life history theory does, but for simplicity we assume there is no aging. Furthermore,
59 each action takes time as in optimal foraging theory. To keep things simple, in our model
60 the activity distribution depends exclusively on the phenotype, whereas in optimal
61 foraging theory the energy intake depends on both the foraging strategy (activity) of the
62 forager and the actual density of food. In optimal foraging theory it was found that the
63 time constraints have essential effect on the optimal foraging strategy (e.g., Stephens &
64 Krebs 1986, Garay & Móri 2010).

65 Our basic assumption is that the individuals may only differ in their activity
66 distributions, but they are alike in all other respects. Consequently, in the present model,
67 the phenotypes are fully defined by their activity distributions. We seek phenotypes
68 which maximize interesting objective functions (cf. Garay et al. 2016, Garay & Varga
69 2005).

70 The challenge is to find the optimal phenotype, i.e., the optimal distribution on the
71 activities. However, this question is ambiguous, since there are trade-offs (i.e., negative
72 correlations) between either fecundity and survival rate, or fecundity and time duration,
73 or both. In general no phenotype maximizes fecundity and survival rate simultaneously.
74 The problem can be made precise mathematically, if we define an objective function, and
75 find the phenotype that maximizes it, thus we seek the optimal phenotype with respect to
76 a prescribed objective function. Now we are facing the problem of choosing the “right”
77 objective function. We mention two biological examples of this trade-off phenomenon,
78 together with an (incomplete) list of some previously proposed objective functions, to
79 demonstrate the ambiguity.

80 Firstly, in the theory of survival cost of reproduction (e.g., Harshman & Zera
81 2007, see also life history theory), it is usually assumed that there is a trade-off between
82 fecundity and survival rate. Four widespread objective functions of this theory are as
83 follows. Fisher (1930) proposed *reproductive value*, and later Schaffer (1974) suggested
84 *optimal reproductive effort*. The selfish individual maximizes her *life reproductive*
85 *success* (e.g., Yearsley et al. 2002), which is the average number of offspring during the
86 individual life span. Finally, the fourth objective function is the *growth rate of a*
87 *phenotype* (e.g., Caswell 2001, Garay et al. 2016).

88 Secondly, in the theory of optimal foraging under predation risk (e.g., Stephens &
89 Krebs 1986, Brown & Kotler 2004), it is usually assumed that there is a trade-off between
90 fecundity and survival rate. A multitude of objective functions have been proposed, as
91 follows. Gilliam (1982) introduced the *mortality per fecundity* rule. Houston et al. (1993)
92 consider two objectives: (a) the animal must collect a fixed amount of food to reproduce;

93 (b) the animal must survive for a fixed time. Finally, Brown & Kotler (2004) study (a)
94 and (b) above, and two further ones: the sum and the product of fecundity and survival
95 rate (see also Bednekoff & Lima 2011). Observe that all cited objective functions refer to
96 either an individual or a phenotype.

97 As noted earlier, the question arises: is there a method for selecting the “correct”
98 objective function, if any? As we will see, the answer is positive. Based on our earlier
99 results we propose the following method (Garay et al. 2016, Garay & Varga 2005).
100 Consider a selection situation with different phenotypes and (at least) two different
101 objective functions. For any pair of different objective functions, there are two
102 possibilities: they attain their maximum either at the same phenotype or at different
103 phenotypes. In the former case there is no difference between them in the given selection
104 situation, while in the latter case we have an evolutionary selection problem, namely, a
105 selection situation with different phenotypes, and we can see which phenotype wins the
106 struggle of coexistence. Thus, we can say that the winner phenotype’s objective function
107 is maximized by selection. For instance, in the recently introduced kin demographic
108 selection model (Garay et al. 2016), the Darwinian phenotype (which maximizes the
109 phenotype’s long term growth rate) is shown to outperform all other possible phenotypes
110 (maximizing other objective functions). That model is based on the classical Leslie
111 model, which assumes age dependent survival rate and fecundity. In the present paper,
112 we investigate whether this recent result remains valid in the different selection situation
113 considered here.

114 In Darwinian evolution theory, natural selection maximizes the fitness of a
115 phenotype. In asexual models, fitness is defined as the average growth rate of the

116 phenotype per capita, i.e., the average number of descendants of an individual with the
117 given phenotype born in a unit of time.

118 Since phenomena in ecology are the results of evolution (Hutchinson 1965), it is
119 reasonable to the fitness (i.e., the average growth rate) is the object of maximization in
120 ecology as well.

121 In the present paper, we consider three objective functions: *the average offspring*
122 *number during life span*, *the probability of non-extinction of descendants*, and *the*
123 *phenotypic growth rate*. By finding the optimal phenotypes with respect to these
124 objective functions, we demonstrate that in the selection situation under study, different
125 objective functions are maximized by different phenotypes, in general. We emphasize
126 that from the mathematical point of view all objective functions are possible.
127 Subsequently, we investigate which phenotype wins the struggle of coexistence. Given
128 that in our selection situation there are no interactions between individuals, one may ask:
129 what kind of competition mechanism can arise, if any? Our selection mechanism is based
130 on the classical Darwinian reasoning (Darwin 1859), namely, though individuals produce
131 more offspring than the carrying capacity, natural selection keeps the population size
132 bounded. In our case, every possible phenotype must have an exponential growth rate in
133 order to exist at all. Since we assumed that phenotypes only differ in their activity
134 distributions, they are equivalent (interchangeable) in this process of survival according
135 to the carrying capacity. Thus in our case natural selection is realized by a random and
136 uniform selection mechanism, where, as we will see, the highest Malthusian parameter
137 will win the struggle of existence (cf. Garay et al. 2016).

138

139 **2. Phenotypes, objective functions, and optimal strategies**

140 Suppose an individual member of a population can choose from r activities
 141 (choice does not necessarily presume deliberation, since in biology a lot of species have a
 142 genetically fixed behavior). Her choice is random: activity s is chosen with probability
 143 p_s , $s = 1, \dots, r$. Clearly, $p_1 + \dots + p_r = 1$. We define a phenotype by this activity
 144 distribution $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_r)$. Activity s takes time τ_s . At the end of the activity the
 145 individual either perishes without descendants, this happens with probability q_s , or the
 146 individual gives birth to c_s offspring, and the whole process starts over: independently of
 147 its past, the survivor makes a new choice, and so on. The progeny size c_s can be random,
 148 but finite expectation (and sometimes more, cf (5) in subsection 2.2) is required. We
 149 assume $0 < q_s < 1$ to exclude trivialities. This ensures that the lifetime of the individual is
 150 finite with probability 1.

151 Let us extend this model by allowing a more general set of activities. Suppose
 152 activities are parametrized from a general measurable space $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{F})$, where the parameter
 153 set \mathcal{S} is called the activity space, its elements represent different activities, and \mathcal{F} is the
 154 σ -field of measurable subsets of \mathcal{S} . Every individual chooses an activity at random,
 155 according to an activity distribution (probability measure) $\mathbf{p} : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow [0, 1]$, called strategy
 156 (phenotype). We suppose that the joint distribution of the triplet (τ_s, q_s, c_s) is a
 157 measurable function of s (this condition holds automatically if the activity space is
 158 countable, since in that case every subset of \mathcal{S} is traditionally supposed measurable). By

159 the law of total probability, the joint distribution of (τ, q, c) is a mixture of the
 160 distributions of (τ_s, q_s, c_s) , $s \in \mathcal{S}$, with mixing measure \mathbf{p} .

161 Each child follows her parent's strategy, and the characteristic triplets of activity
 162 times, terminal probabilities, and offspring numbers of different individuals are
 163 independent and identically distributed.

164 Successfulness of a strategy can be measured in several ways. Concentrating on
 165 the individual, the measure of success is the average number of offspring produced
 166 during the whole lifetime. On the other hand, if, following Darwin, we concentrate on the
 167 phenotype, then we have to deal with the growth rate of the number of living
 168 descendants. However, the average size of progeny can also be large in such a way that
 169 with a considerable probability there are no living descendants at all, but otherwise a
 170 reproduction boom takes place. Thus it is meaningful to use the probability of non-
 171 extinction of the phenotype as an alternative index.

172 Let us compute these quantities. We will also investigate which strategies
 173 optimize them.

174

175 **2.1. Selfish individual** \mathbf{p}_l maximizes the average offspring number of an individual.

176 Let X denote the number of descendants produced by an individual during her whole
 177 lifetime (several activity cycles). If the individual does not perish without reproduction at
 178 the end of the first activity period, the remainder of her life has the same distribution as if
 179 it were born at the very moment. Thus, if she chooses activity s , the average number of
 180 her offspring equals zero with probability q_s , and $\mathbf{E}c_s + \mathbf{E}X$ with probability $1 - q_s$.

181 Hence, by the theorem of total expectation we can write

182
$$EX = \int_{\mathcal{S}} (1 - q_s)(Ec_s + EX) \mathbf{p}(ds), \quad (1)$$

183 from which

184
$$EX = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{S}} (1 - q_s) Ec_s \mathbf{p}(ds)}{1 - \int_{\mathcal{S}} (1 - q_s) \mathbf{p}(ds)} = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{S}} (1 - q_s) Ec_s \mathbf{p}(ds)}{\int_{\mathcal{S}} q_s \mathbf{p}(ds)} \quad (2)$$

185 follows, provided the average number of offspring in one cycle is finite, that is,
 186 $\int_{\mathcal{S}} (1 - q_s) Ec_s \mathbf{p}(ds) < \infty$. In fact, equation (1) is also satisfied by $EX = \infty$, but it cannot
 187 occur, since the number of activity cycles before death can be majorized by geometric
 188 distribution, which is of finite expectation.

189 Note that in the calculation above the activity lengths τ_s did not appear directly.
 190 They are only present in the effect they have on the number of offspring.

191 Let us find the strategy \mathbf{p}_I that maximizes EX .

192 Since $EX = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{S}} q_s a_s \mathbf{p}(ds)}{\int_{\mathcal{S}} q_s \mathbf{p}(ds)}$, where $a_s = \frac{(1 - q_s) Ec_s}{q_s}$, it can easily be seen that

193
$$EX \leq \sup_{\mathcal{S}} a_s = \sup_{\mathcal{S}} \frac{(1 - q_s) Ec_s}{q_s},$$

194 and equality holds if and only if \mathbf{p}_I is concentrated on activities s for which a_s is equal to
 195 its supremum (if it is attained at all).

196

197 **Remark 1.** We note that the same objective function is used in the problem of optimal
 198 foraging under predation danger (e.g. Clark & Dukas 1994, Higginson & Houston 2015).

199

200 **2.2. Darwinian phenotype** \mathbf{p}_D maximizes the average growth rate of the phenotype, i.e.,
 201 the growth rate of the expected number of living descendants, as time tends to infinity.
 202 For the computation we need to change our viewpoint. Instead of letting an individual
 203 repeat her activity/reproduction cycles until death, we consider the end of the first activity
 204 period as the end of life, and, in the case where the individual would survive the period,
 205 we consider her as one of her siblings. Thus, we now think of τ_s as life span, and the
 206 offspring number ξ_s is defined to be 0 with probability q_s , and $1+c_s$ with probability
 207 $1-q_s$. One can express q_s and c_s in terms of ξ_s , for $q_s = \mathbf{P}(\xi_s = 0)$, and the distribution
 208 of c_s is equal to the conditional distribution of $\xi_s - 1$, provided $\xi_s > 0$. Let τ and ξ
 209 denote the life span and offspring size of the individual, resp., when it chooses strategy \mathbf{p}
 210 (that is, their distribution is a mixture of (τ_s, ξ_s) with mixing measure \mathbf{p}). Let Z_t denote
 211 the population size at time t . This way we obtain an age dependent branching process, or
 212 in other words, a so called Crump–Mode–Jagers (CMJ) process (Haccou et al. 2005),
 213 with reproduction process $\eta(t) = 1_{\{\tau \leq t\}} \xi = \int_S 1_{\{\tau_s \leq t\}} \xi_s \mathbf{p}(ds)$, where $1_{\{\cdot\}}$ stands for the
 214 indicator of the event in brackets. ($\eta(t)$ is the number of offspring up to time t : it is either
 215 0 or $1+c_s$ if the activity period, now lifetime, is already over by t , and 0 otherwise.)
 216 Since reproduction is only allowed at the end of the lifetime, we have a well known and
 217 widely studied particular case of CMJ processes: a Sevast’yanov process. An informal
 218 introduction to CMJ processes is provided in Appendix A. We may and will suppose that
 219 our process is supercritical, that is,

$$220 \quad 1 < \mathbf{E} \xi = \int_S (1 - q_s)(1 + \mathbf{E} c_s) \mathbf{p}(ds) < \infty. \quad (3)$$

221 From the general theory it follows that Z_t grows exponentially with exponent $\alpha > 0$
 222 called the *Malthusian parameter*. It can be obtained as follows. Let $\mu(t)$ denote the
 223 expected number of children born up to time t , that is, $\mu(t) = \mathbb{E}\left(\mathbf{1}_{\{\tau \leq t\}} \xi\right)$. Then $\mu(t)$ is
 224 bounded, for $\mu(\infty) = \mathbb{E} \xi < \infty$. The Malthusian parameter α is the only positive solution
 225 of the equation

$$226 \quad \int_0^\infty e^{-\alpha t} \mu(dt) = \mathbb{E}(e^{-\alpha \tau} \xi) = \int_S \mathbb{E}(e^{-\alpha \tau_s} \xi_s) \mathbf{p}(ds) = 1, \quad (4)$$

227 see Appendix A. The left hand side, as function of α , is continuous, and strictly
 228 decreases from $\mu(\infty) = \mathbb{E} \xi > 1$ to 0 by the monotone convergence theorem.

229 In order to apply the Theorem and Remark of Appendix A we have to check the

230 moment condition. Clearly, $M = \int_0^\infty e^{-\alpha t} \eta(dt) = e^{-\alpha \tau} \xi \leq \xi$, thus it suffices to require that

$$231 \quad \mathbb{E}(\xi \log \xi) = \int_S (1 - q_s) \mathbb{E}[(1 + c_s) \log(1 + c_s)] \mathbf{p}(ds) < \infty. \quad (5)$$

232 Now, using formulae (8) and (9), we can characterize the growth of Z_t .

233 If the distribution of τ is non-lattice, that is, not concentrated on any lattice
 234 $\{0, h, 2h, 3h, \dots\}$, $h > 0$, then

$$235 \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e^{-\alpha t} \mathbb{E} Z_t = K := \frac{\int_0^\infty e^{-\alpha t} \mathbb{E} \phi(t) dt}{\int_0^\infty t e^{-\alpha t} \mu(dt)} = \frac{\mathbb{E}(1 - e^{-\alpha \tau})}{\alpha \mathbb{E}(\tau e^{-\alpha \tau} \xi)} = \frac{\int_S \mathbb{E}(1 - e^{-\alpha \tau_s}) \mathbf{p}(ds)}{\alpha \int_S \mathbb{E}(\tau_s e^{-\alpha \tau_s} \xi_s) \mathbf{p}(ds)}. \quad (6)$$

236 Moreover, $e^{-\alpha t} Z_t$ converges to a random variable W almost surely, $\mathbb{E} W = K$, and W is
 237 positive almost everywhere outside the set of extinction.

238 If the distribution of τ is lattice, say τ is integer valued (the case of discrete
239 time), then for integer t we have $Z_t \sim W e^{\alpha t}$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$, where now

$$240 \quad EW = K = \lim_{\substack{t \rightarrow \infty \\ t \text{ integer}}} e^{-\alpha t} \mathbf{E}Z_t = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{E}(1 - e^{-\alpha \tau_s}) \mathbf{p}(ds)}{(1 - e^{-\alpha}) \int_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{E}(\tau_s e^{-\alpha \tau_s} \xi_s) \mathbf{p}(ds)}. \quad (7)$$

241 Consequently, the Malthusian parameter α appears to be an adequate measure of
242 successfulness in the Darwinian sense, both in the lattice and non-lattice cases.

243

244 *Maximal average growth of phenotype.* Let us find the strategy \mathbf{p}_D that maximizes α .

245 Suppose $\mathbf{E}\xi_s = (1 - q_s)(1 + \mathbf{E}c_s) > 1$ for some $s \in \mathcal{S}$. Let α_s denote the Malthusian

246 parameter associated with the pair (τ_s, ξ_s) , that is, the only positive solution of the

247 equation $\mathbf{E}(e^{-\alpha \tau_s} \xi_s) = 1$. We will show that the optimal rate is

$$248 \quad \alpha_D = \sup\{\alpha_s : \mathbf{E}\xi_s > 1\},$$

249 and it can be attained if and only if \mathbf{p}_D is concentrated on activities s for which α_s is

250 maximal. Indeed, for every $s \in \mathcal{S}$ we have $\mathbf{E}(e^{-\alpha_D \tau_s} \xi_s) \leq 1$, hence

$$251 \quad \int_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{E}(e^{-\alpha_D \tau_s} \xi_s) \mathbf{p}(ds) \leq 1, \text{ implying } \alpha \leq \alpha_D. \text{ The condition of equality is obvious.}$$

252 In the particular case of constant activity times, the Malthusian equation reads

$$253 \quad \sum_{s=1}^r p_s (1 - q_s) (1 + \mathbf{E}c_s) e^{-\alpha \tau_s} = 1,$$

254 and the maximum of the Malthusian parameter is equal to

$$255 \quad \alpha_D = \max_{1 \leq s \leq r} \frac{\log[(1 - q_s)(1 + \mathbf{E}c_s)]}{\tau_s}.$$

256

257 **Remark 2.** When all survival rates are the same (i.e., $q_s = q$), the maximal possible
 258 growth rate of the phenotype is similar to the objective function of optimal foraging
 259 theory, namely, to the maximum of the intake energy rate in the case when one type of
 260 prey is more profitable than the other ones (e.g., Stephens & Krebs 1986).

261

262 **2.3. Survival phenotype \mathbf{p}_e** minimizes the extinction probability of phenotype, or, in
 263 other words, maximizes the probability of phenotype survival. Though in the supercritical
 264 case the mean population size tends to infinity at an exponential rate, the phenotype can
 265 still become extinct with positive – occasionally high – probability. An alternative
 266 criterion of optimality can be the probability of the survival of the phenotype, that is, one
 267 can aim at minimizing the probability π of extinction.

268

269 In the age-dependent branching model this probability can easily be found by
 270 considering the discrete time Galton–Watson process embedded in the general
 271 Sevast’yanov process. Starting from a single ancestor, let us call her offspring the first
 272 generation, the offspring of the first generation the second generation, and so on. Then
 273 the successive generations form a Galton–Watson process with offspring size ξ . The
 274 extinction probability π is the smallest positive solution of the equation $\pi = g(\pi)$,
 275 where $g(x) = \mathbf{E}(x^\xi)$, the probability generating function of ξ (see Theorem 2.3.1. of
 276 Jagers 1975). Particularly, let $g_s(x) = q_s + (1 - q_s)x\mathbf{E}(x^{c_s})$, then $g(x) = \int_S g_s(x)\mathbf{p}(ds)$.

277

278 *Minimal extinction probability.* Let us find the strategy \mathbf{p}_e that minimizes π . First we
 279 show that the infimum of the extinction probability as \mathbf{p} runs over all possible strategies
 280 is equal to $\pi_e = \inf_{\mathcal{S}} \pi_s$, where π_s is the extinction probability under the pure strategy s ,
 281 that is, the smallest positive solution of the equation $g_s(x) = x$. Thus, π_e is the infimum
 282 of π over all pure strategies.

283 Indeed, since $g_s(x)$, being a probability generating function itself, downcrosses
 284 the identity function at π_s , we have $g_s(x) \geq x$ for $x \leq \pi_s$. Therefore,

$$285 \quad g(\pi_e) = \int_{\mathcal{S}} g_s(\pi_e) \mathbf{p}(ds) \geq \int_{\mathcal{S}} \pi_e \mathbf{p}(ds) = \pi_e,$$

286 implying that π_e is less than or equal to the extinction probability under an arbitrary
 287 strategy \mathbf{p} . On the other hand, we can get arbitrarily close to π_e by using pure strategies
 288 only.

289 An equivalent characterization of π_e is the following. Introduce the function

$$290 \quad f(x) = \inf_{\mathcal{S}} g_s(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1.$$

291 Then π_e is the largest solution of the equation $x = f(x)$ in the interval $[0, 1)$. Indeed, for
 292 every positive ε there exists an $s \in \mathcal{S}$ such that $\pi_s \leq \pi_e + \varepsilon$, hence

$$293 \quad f(\pi_e) \leq f(\pi_s) \leq g_s(\pi_s) = \pi_s \leq \pi_e + \varepsilon.$$

294 Thus $f(\pi_e) \leq \pi_e$. On the other hand, for every positive ε there exists an $s \in \mathcal{S}$ such that

$$295 \quad g_s(\pi_e) \leq f(\pi_e) + \varepsilon. \text{ Since } \pi_e \leq \pi_s, \text{ we have } \pi_e \leq g_s(\pi_e), \text{ and by that, } \pi_e \leq f(\pi_e).$$

296 Finally, if $\pi_e < x < 1$, then there exists an $s \in \mathcal{S}$ such that $\pi_s < x$, thus $f(x) \leq g_s(x) < x$.

297 Clearly, strategy \mathbf{p} attains π_e if and only if it is concentrated on activities s for
 298 which $\pi_s = \pi_e$.

299

300 Observe that the above objective functions can generally take their maximums at
 301 different strategies \mathbf{p} . On the other hand, if the same activity has the largest survival
 302 probability, the highest fecundity, and the shortest time duration, then it maximizes all
 303 considered objective functions simultaneously.

304

305 **Example 1.** Consider the following parameters. For the sake of simplicity, both the
 306 offspring size and the time duration are non-random.

	Activity 1	Activity 2	Activity 3
Probability of death, q	$q_1 = 0.4$	$q_2 = 0.4$	$q_3 = 0.2$
Offspring size, c	$c_1 = 11$	$c_2 = 8$	$c_3 = 3$
Time duration τ	$\tau_1 = 5$	$\tau_2 = 1$	$\tau_3 = 5$

307

Table 1. *A simple model with three activities.*

308 For the pair of activities 1 and 2, there is a trade-off between fecundity and time
 309 duration. Moreover, for the pair of activities 2 and 3, there is a trade-off between
 310 fecundity and survival rate. Simple calculations show that the selfish individual must
 311 choose activity 1, the Darwinian phenotype activity 2, while the survival phenotype uses
 312 activity 3.

313

	Activity 1	Activity 2	Activity 3
Mean offspring size	$EX = 16.5$	$EX = 12$	$EX = 12$
Growth rate (Malthusian parameter)	$\alpha_1 = 0.394$	$\alpha_2 = 1.686$	$\alpha_3 = 0.232$
Probability of extinction	$\pi_1 = 0.400$	$\pi_2 = 0.400$	$\pi_3 = 0.201$

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Table 2. *Values of objective functions for the activities in Table 1.*

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Intuitively, the selfish individual concentrates on the number of her own offspring. The Darwinian phenotype also takes account of the number of its children, grandchildren, great-grandchildren, and so on, and how fast its reproduction can be. The survival phenotype concentrates on the long time survival of its posterity.

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3. A simple selection model

331 We consider a monomorphic model where in a resident population a mutant
332 phenotype appears, and natural selection has sufficient time to select out the less fit
333 phenotype.

334 In Section 2 we determined the optimal phenotypes corresponding to different
335 objective functions. Clearly, if two phenotypes have different activity distributions, they
336 generally have different growth rates (Malthusian parameters) α . Let us consider the
337 Darwinian phenotype with Malthusian parameter α_D and a mutant phenotype with a
338 smaller $\alpha_M < \alpha_D$. Let f_D resp. f_M denote the frequencies of Darwinian resp. mutant
339 phenotypes.

340 When the rare mutants appear, there are two possibilities: they either die out
341 within a short time due to random fluctuation (we will not investigate this case), or the
342 mutant phenotype survives for such a long time that it reaches its asymptotic growth rate.
343 Since evolution is a long process, we are interested in the second possibility. Let T_R
344 denote the time duration of the long reproductive season, when different phenotypes
345 reproduce according to their activity distributions. When the reproductive season is over,
346 the size of the population decreases in accordance with the carrying capacity. One may
347 think of the reproductive season as taking place during spring and summer time, when the
348 activity determines the survival rate and the fecundity of individuals; moreover, the
349 average number of generations during the reproductive season is determined by the time
350 durations. Assume that the reproductive season is long enough to allow a high number of
351 generations, i.e. $T_R \gg \max \tau_i$. The carrying capacity is determined by the winter time,
352 when the whole population size is reduced to the carrying capacity by a uniform survival

353 process, which equally affects all phenotypes, i.e., the survival rates are all equal (by our
354 basic assumption, phenotypes differ only in their activity distribution).

355 Let us denote the carrying capacity by C , supposed sufficiently large. Clearly,
356 $C = f_D + f_M$. Since C is large, we can describe selection as a “mass process”, i.e.,
357 random fluctuations have no effect on the number of individuals (at least in the order of
358 magnitude). If there are many individuals of a given phenotype, the probability of
359 eventual extinction, being a negative exponential function of the phenotype size, is
360 negligible. Hence, at the end of the reproductive season (before the selection according to
361 carrying capacity) the approximate sizes of the Darwinian, resp. mutant phenotypes are
362 $f_D K_D e^{\alpha_D T_R}$ and $f_M K_M e^{\alpha_M T_R}$, where K_D and K_M denote the current values of the
363 constant K appearing in formulae (6) and (7). Since the considered phenotypes are
364 equivalent with respect to the carrying capacity, each individual will survive with

365 probability $\rho \approx \frac{C}{f_D K_D e^{\alpha_D T_R} + f_M K_M e^{\alpha_M T_R}}$, so after selection, at the beginning of the

366 next reproductive season, the phenotype sizes are $f'_D \approx \rho f_D K_D e^{\alpha_D T_R}$ and
367 $f'_M \approx \rho f_M K_M e^{\alpha_M T_R}$, resp. Therefore, the ratio of mutant and Darwinian phenotype
368 frequencies will decrease very fast, namely, at a rate exponential in the number of
369 reproductive seasons:

370
$$\frac{f'_M}{f'_D} \approx \frac{f_M}{f_D} \cdot Q, \text{ where } Q = \frac{K_M}{K_D} e^{-(\alpha_D - \alpha_M) T_R} \ll 1.$$

371 We emphasize that Darwinian phenotype does not only win against selfish and
372 survival phenotypes, but it outperforms all other phenotypes based on different objective

373 functions mentioned in Introduction (unless an objective function happens to take its
374 maximum just at the Darwinian phenotype).

375

376 **5. Conclusion**

377 We considered an asexual, sufficiently large and non-ageing population, where
378 the generations are overlapping, and there is no mutation and no interaction between
379 individuals. The individuals engage in activities, which determine their fecundity and
380 survival probability, moreover these activities take time. A phenotype is identified with a
381 probability distribution on the activities. Our aim was to find the phenotype with optimal
382 evolutionary behavior. The natural candidates are phenotypes which maximize one or
383 another objective function, a multitude of which have already been proposed in the
384 literature. Generally, different objective functions are maximized by different
385 phenotypes. However, without introducing a selection mechanism we cannot find out
386 which phenotype outperforms all other ones. To this end, we proposed a selection
387 method: since in our case the individuals do not interact, and all phenotypes contend
388 under the same conditions, therefore the competition of phenotypes must be uniform. We
389 pointed out that actually the different objective functions (e.g., different definitions of
390 fitness) are the objects of natural selection. We showed that the Darwinian phenotype,
391 which maximizes the average growth rate of the phenotype, outperforms all other
392 phenotypes under consideration (those maximizing the individual's average offspring
393 number during life span or minimizing the extinction probability of descendants, and so
394 on). From the aspect of theoretical biology, this means that the fitness of a phenotype is

395 best defined by the average growth rate of the phenotype in the selection situation where
396 each activity may have different survival rate, fecundity, and time duration.

397 We have already mentioned that, from the mathematical point of view, our
398 selection situation is possibly the simplest mathematical combination of life history
399 theory and optimal foraging theory. Our objective functions correspond to some objective
400 functions already introduced in optimal foraging theory (Remarks 1 and 2). We
401 conjecture that the Darwinian phenotype wins the struggle of existence more generally,
402 namely, if one lets the time durations of activities be influenced by prey densities in an
403 unbounded and aging population, As an outlook, we mention a few selection situations,
404 where the Darwinian phenotype outperforms other ones. Firstly, in kin selection theory
405 (Hamilton 1964), the altruistic phenotype (at a cost to the own survival and reproduction)
406 helps the reproductive success of one of its own relatives. Secondly, in the kin
407 demography model, it can be pointed out that sib cannibalism between closest relatives
408 can be considered as an extreme mutualism (Garay et al. 2016).

409 Finally, we note that our result could be applied in both optimal foraging theory
410 and life history theory, where there is a trade-off between any pair of the offspring
411 number, survival rate, and time duration. Our model can deal with these trade-offs, since
412 we do not impose assumptions on the correlation between parameters. An important
413 consequence of our model is that, independently of the “objective functions”, the optimal
414 behavior can always be achieved by pure strategies, i.e., with a single activity. Thus, our
415 results offer the possibility to test, either by experiment or by field observation, which
416 objective function is optimized by natural selection.

417

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423

424 **References**

- 425 Bednekoff, P.A., Lima, S.L., 2011. Risk allocation is a general phenomenon: A reply to
426 Beauchamp and Ruxton. *Am. Nat.* 177, 147–151. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/657440>
- 427 Brown, J.S., Kotler, B.P., 2004. Hazardous duty pay and the foraging cost of predation.
428 *Ecol. Lett.* 7, 999–1014. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2004.00661.x>
- 429 Caswell, H., 2001. *Matrix Population Models: Construction, Analysis and Interpretation*,
430 2nd Edition. Sinauer Associates, Sunderland, MA, ISBN-13: 9780878930968
- 431 Charnov, E.L., 1993. *Life History Invariants: Some Explorations of Symmetry in*
432 *Evolutionary Ecology*. Oxford University Press, Oxford. ISBN-13: 978-0198540717
- 433 Clark, C.W., Dukas, R., 1994. Balancing foraging and antipredator demands: An
434 advantage of sociality. *Am. Nat.* 144, 542–548. <http://dx.doi.org/doi:10.1086/285693>
- 435 Darwin, C., 1859. *On the Origin of Species by Means of Natural Selection, or the*
436 *Preservation of Favoured Races in the Struggle for Life*. John Murray, London.
437 ISBN-13: 978-0553214635
- 438 Fisher, R.A., 1930. *The Genetical Theory of Natural Selection*. The Clarendon Press,
439 Oxford. ISBN-13: 978-1406707830

- 440 Garay, J. Móri, T.F., 2010, When is the opportunism remunerative? *Community Ecol.* 11,
441 160–170. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1556/ComEc.11.2010.2.4>
- 442 Garay, J., Varga, Z., 2005. Evolutionary dynamics for economic behaviour: competition
443 versus optimization. *Pure Math. Appl.* 16, 399–409.
- 444 Garay, J., Varga, Z., Gámez, M., Cabello, T., 2016. Sib cannibalism can be adaptive for
445 kin. *Ecol. Model.* 334, 51–59. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2016.05.001>
- 446 Gilliam, J.F., 1982. *Foraging under mortality risk in size-structured population*. Ph.D.
447 diss. Michigan State Univ., East Lansing, MI
- 448 Hamilton, W.D., 1964. The genetical evolution of social behaviour I. *J. Theor. Biol.* 7, 1–
449 9. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0022-5193\(64\)90038-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0022-5193(64)90038-4)
- 450 Harshman, L.G., Zera, A.J., 2007. The cost of reproduction: the devil in the details.
451 *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 22, 80–86. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2006.10.008>
- 452 Haccou, P., Jagers, P., Vatunin, V.A., 2005. *Branching Processes: Variation, Growth,*
453 *and Extinction of Populations*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. ISBN-13:
454 978-0521832205.
- 455 Higginson, A.D., Houston, A.I., 2015. The influence of the food: predation trade-off on
456 the foraging behaviour of central-place foragers. *Behav. Ecol. Sociobiol.* 69, 551–561.
457 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00265-014-1866-9>
- 458 Houston, A.I., McNamara, J.M., Hutchinson, J.M.C., 1993. General results concerning
459 the trade-off between gaining energy and avoiding predation. *Philos. T. Roy. Soc. B.*
460 341, 375–397. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rstb.1993.0123>
- 461 Hutchinson G.E., 1965. *The Ecological Theater and the Evolutionary Play*. Yale
462 University Press, New Haven, Connecticut. ISBN-13: 978-0300005868

- 463 Jagers, P., 1975. *Branching Processes with Biological Applications*. John Wiley & Sons,
464 London-New York-Sydney-Toronto. ISBN-13: 978-0471436522
- 465 Nerman, O., 1981. On the convergence of supercritical general (C-M-J) branching
466 processes. *Z. Wahrscheinlichkeitstheorie verw. Gebiete*, 57, 365–395.
467 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF00534830>
- 468 Schaffer, W.M., 1974. Selection for optimal life histories: The effects of age structure.
469 *Ecology* 55, 291–303. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/1935217>
- 470 Stearns, S., 1992. *The Evolution of Life Histories*. Oxford University Press, Oxford,
471 ISBN-13: 978-0198577416
- 472 Stephens, D.W., Krebs, J.R., 1986. *Foraging Theory*. Princeton University Press,
473 Princeton. ISBN-13: 978-0691084428
- 474 Yearsley, J., Hastings, I.M., Gordon, I.J., Kyriazakis, I., Illius, A.W., 2002. A Lifetime
475 perspective on foraging and mortality. *J. Theor. Biol.* 215, 385–397.
476 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/jtbi.2002.2529>

477

478 **Appendix A.**

479 In this section, we give an informal introduction to general time dependent
480 branching processes, or Crump–Mode–Jagers (CMJ) processes. The interested reader
481 may find more formal descriptions in the monographs (Jagers 1975) or (Haccou et al.
482 2005).

483 In a CMJ branching process there are individuals who reproduce and die. This is
484 characterized by a random point process $\eta(t)$, $t \geq 0$, called the reproduction process, and
485 a nonnegative random variable τ , which is the life span. They are not supposed

486 independent. The random variable $\eta(t)$ is the number of offspring up to time t . Most
 487 often there is no reproduction after death, i.e., $\eta(t) = \eta(\tau)$ for $t > \tau$ (but this is not
 488 necessarily required).

489 The life history of every individual e is described by the pair $(\eta_e(\cdot), \tau_e)$; they are
 490 independent and identically distributed copies of $(\eta(\cdot), \tau)$ introduced above. If individual
 491 e was born at time σ_e , then at time t the number of her children (dead or alive) is
 492 $\eta_e(t - \sigma_e)$ ($\eta_e(t)$ is defined as zero for negative t), and it decreases at time $\sigma_e + \tau_e$. We
 493 are interested in the number of individuals alive at time t , which we will denote by Z_t .

494 A CMJ process is called *subcritical*, *critical*, or *supercritical*, according that the
 495 expected number of offspring of an individual, $\mathbb{E}[\eta(\infty)]$, is less than, equal to, or greater
 496 than 1, respectively. In the sequel we are interested in supercritical processes. For the
 497 sake of simplicity we only formulate the basic limit theorem in the form we need it, not in
 498 its most general form, because we want to apply it to a model with nice properties.

499 Therefore we suppose that $1 < \mathbb{E}[\eta(\infty)] < \infty$. Such processes grow exponentially fast on
 500 the event of non-extinction. The rate of growth is described by the so called Malthusian

501 parameter α . It is the only positive solution of the equation $\int_0^\infty e^{-\alpha t} \mu(dt) = 1$, where

502 $\mu(t) = \mathbb{E}[\eta(t)]$, the expected number of offspring of an individual up to time t after her
 503 birth.

504 Combining Proposition 2.2, Theorems 3.1 and 5.4 of (Nerman 1981), we get the
 505 following limit theorem.

506

507 **Theorem.** *With the definition $M = \int_0^\infty e^{-\alpha t} \eta(dt)$, suppose that $E[M \log^+ M] < \infty$ holds.*
 508 *Furthermore, suppose the Lebesgue–Stieltjes measure generated by μ is not lattice, i.e.,*
 509 *$\mu(t)$ is not a piecewise constant function with points of increase all belonging to a lattice*
 510 *$\{0, h, 2h, 3h, \dots\}$, $h > 0$. Then*

511
$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e^{-\alpha t} E Z_t = K := \frac{\int_0^\infty e^{-\alpha t} P(\tau > t) dt}{\int_0^\infty t e^{-\alpha t} \mu(dt)}. \quad (8)$$

512 *Moreover, $e^{-\alpha t} Z_t$ converges to a random variable W almost surely, $EW = K$, and W is*
 513 *positive almost everywhere outside the set of extinction.*

514

515 **Remark.** *If μ is lattice, that is, when an individual can reproduce only at times that are*
 516 *multiples of h (the case of discrete time), then formula (8) slightly changes. Without loss*
 517 *of generality we can suppose that $h = 1$. Then for integer t we have $Z_t \sim W e^{\alpha t}$ as*
 518 *$t \rightarrow \infty$, where*

519
$$EW = \frac{\alpha}{1 - e^{-\alpha}} \cdot \frac{\int_0^\infty e^{-\alpha t} P(\tau > t) dt}{\int_0^\infty t e^{-\alpha t} \mu(dt)}. \quad (9)$$